

Dra1 - RFLP patterns of introgression lines (*O. sativa*/*O. granulata*). Lanes. λ - molecular weight marker; 1-10 and 14-23 - different derived lines; 11 - *O. sativa* IR31917-45-3-2; 12- *O. granulata* (acc. 100879); 13-F₁ hybrid. a) Probe RZ884, chromosome 6. See *O. granulata*-specific allele in lanes 2 and 3 (marked with arrow). b) Probe R2797, chromosome 11. Nonparental band in lane 1 and *O. granulata* alleles in derived-MAALs for chromosome 11 (lanes 6 and 7).

Acrotrisomics in rice

K. Ikeda, H. Furuumi, A. Yoshimura, H. Yasui, and N. Iwata, Plant Breeding Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Kyushu University, Fukuoka 812-81, Japan

Researchers have extensively used primary trisomics in genetic mapping of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). However, no information

existed previously on the occurrence of acrotrisomics in rice.

We isolated six acrotrisomic plants from selfed progenies of primary trisomics and from the F₁ obtained from pollination of primary trisomics with irradiated pollen. An extra chromosome was identified in these acrotrisomics. One of the acrotrisomics was used in chromosome mapping.

Triplo 4, with liguleless gene (*lg lg lg*), and Triplo 7 were used for crossing as female plants. Among the F₁ plants,

acrotrisomic-like plants were selected based on the phenomenon of pseudo-dominance (Triplo 4) and abnormal morphological characters (Triplo 7). In the progenies of primary trisomics (Triplo 4, 5, 7, and 11), acrotrisomic-like plants showed abnormal morphological characters spontaneously.

Among the selected plants, six acrotrisomics were identified by mitotic chromosome analysis (Acro4S^{4L}-a, Acro4S^{4L}-b, Acro5, Acro 11) and/or restriction fragment

length polymorphism (RFLP) gene dosage analysis (Acro4S^{4L}-a, Acro7a, Acro7b). To distinguish two Acro4S^{4L} isolated from different origins, the acrotrisomics were designated as Acro4S^{4L}-a and Acro4S^{4L}-b, and Acro7.

Acro4S^{4L}-a and Acro7a were selected in the F₁ plants; the other acrotrisomics were obtained from the progenies of primary trisomics. Acro4S^{4L}-a and Acro4S^{4L}-b each had a complete short arm (4S) and heterochromatin region of the long arm (4L) on chromosome 4 in addition to a normal chromosome complement as identified by mitotic chromosome analysis. RFLP gene dosage analyses were studied based on RFLP map (Saito et al 1991). RFLP gene dosage effects of Acro4S^{4L}-a were observed at the loci on *XNpb203*, *237*, and *311* but not at the loci on *XNpb49*, *114*, and *120* on chromosome 4. These plants had narrow grains, as did those of Acro4S^{4L}-b.

Acro5 had a fragment of about one-third of chromosome 5, and the plants had small grains and short panicles. RFLP gene dosage effects of Acro7a and Acro7b were observed at the locus of *XNpb338* but not at the loci *XNpb33* to *22* on chromosome 7. These plants had compact panicles and round grains. Acro11 had a fragment containing heterochromatin. Morphological features of the plants were late heading and short stature.

The acrocentric chromosome of each acrotrisomic was easily transmitted to the

Breeding behavior of acrotrisomics upon selfing.

Acrotrisomic	Plants (%)			Plants (no.)
	Disomics	Acrotrisomics	Primary trisomics	
Acro4S ^{4L} -a	55.2	35.8	9.1	618
Acro4S ^{4L} -b	61.9	37.1	0.9	854
Acro5	59.4	38.1	2.5	286
Acro7a	71.3	27.3	1.5	891
Acro7b	66.4	30.6	3.0	265
Av (total)	63.5	33.3	3.2	(2914)

next generation. The average frequency of acrotrisomics in the selfed progenies of five acrotrisomics was 33.3%, ranging from 27.3% in Acro7a to 38.1% in Acro5 (see table).

RFLP gene dosage analysis of Acro4S^{4L}-a suggested that the break point of the acrocentric chromosome was in the region between *XNpb311* and *49* (10.5 cM) on chromosome 4, and that the chromosome lacked the region from *XNpb49* to *lg* on the long arm. These findings and integrated linkage map (Ideta et al 1992) revealed the orientation of the marker genes on chromosome 4 (see figure). The arrangement of classical and RFLP marker genes from the long arm are *lg-XNpb120-114-d-11-49-311-237-203*.

Cited references

Ideta O, Yoshimura A, Matsumo T, Tsunematsu H, Iwata N. 1992. Integration of conventional and RFLP linkage maps in rice. I. Chromosomes 1, 2, 3, and 4. Rice Genet. Newsl. 9:128-129.

Construction of chromosome 4 map using acrotrisomic-Acro4S^{4L}-a: classical linkage map (left), RFLP linkage map (center), and ideogram of chromosome 4 (right).

^a Italicized numbers indicate RFLP markers.

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Molecular mapping of fertility-restoring gene *Rf3* in rice

G. Zhang and Y. Lu, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, China; and N. Huang, IRRRI

Cytoplasmic male sterility in WA-Zhen-shan 97 A (ZSA), a male sterile line widely used for developing hybrid rice in China, is caused by the interaction between wild abortive cytoplasm and two nuclear genes.

A series of near-isogenic lines (NILs) carrying different genotypes for restoration was developed by nine backcrosses to ZSA using IR24, a restorer line with two fertility-restoring genes, as the donor (Zhang et al 1994).

To tag the restorer genes, the set of NILs and the donor IR24 were used for randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) analysis. From a survey of 720 random primers, we identified six RAPD markers that were associated with one of the two restorer genes. Three of the six RAPD markers (OPK05-800, OPU10-1100, and OPW01-350) were used as probes. They were located on chromosome 1 in a population of doubled haploid lines derived from cross IR64/Azucena.

An F₂ population was developed from the cross between ZSA and ZSRR21. ZSRR21 is a NIL carrying two restorer genes. Thirty-six sterile plants in the F₂ segregating population were selected for linkage analysis. The three RAPD markers and three restriction fragment length

polymorphism markers (RG532, RG140, and RG458 located on chromosome 1) were found to be closely linked to the restorer gene. The distances between each of the six markers and the restorer gene were less than 4 cM in this population (see figure).

For fertility restorer genes in rice, *Rf1* was the notation given to the gene located on chromosome 10, which restores male fertility in line CMS-B (Shinryo 1975). *Rf2* was the notation given to the gene located on chromosome 2, which restores male fertility in line CMS-L (Shinryo and Sato 1994). In this study, the restorer gene located on chromosome 2, named *Rf2* in a previous paper, is named *Rf3* (Zhang et al 1994).